

METHODS TO ENHANCE STUDENTS’ ENGLISH-SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract: Nowadays more people are spending time to learn English as a second language. Everybody wants to speak like a native speaker and without any grammatical mistakes. Speaking is one of the four macro skills that need to be developed. Developing it is a crucial problem for majority of learners. Learning how to develop the English speaking ability is so important for ESL students and EAL students too. This article discusses various speaking methods which focus on improving speaking skills, expanding vocabulary, building strong speaking confidence and foundation, speech shadowing*(learning through imitating) for a non-native speaker as well as conquering receptive bilingualism*(understanding but not speaking a language). And it will be also helpful for representing various competitions like Debates, Elocution, Story writing and Public Speakings.

Key words: Speaking ability, Speaking methods, Receptive Bilingualism, Oral Communication, Students prospective

English as the Language of International Communication plays an essential role in our lives. But what is the main purpose of learning English? English is the language of technology, science, industry, business, internet, tourism, computers and so on. Knowing English increases your chances of getting a job in any kind of country and it also helps you to see things from a different perspective. English is important for communicating and socializing. If you are still not sure about whether to learn the language, then check out the reasons below.

6 reasons to learn English

- ◆Communicating with new people
- ◆Getting a deeper understanding of another culture
- ◆Studying English can help you to get a job
- ◆Travelling is a lot easier with good knowledge of English
- ◆If you know English you can study all over the world

◆By knowing English, you can also understand the media industry

Speaking can be complicated for non-native speakers. While improving speaking skills students prospective is vital because this age is the age of mass communication, media, agitation. Speech is the prime means of communication and the structure of the society itself would be substantially different if we had failed to develop communication through speech (John Laver, 1994). Through speaking we can express our thoughts easily. Speaking is the verbal use of language and a medium through which human beings communicate with each other (Fulcher, 2003). While speaking in a foreign language you might not be confident as in your native language. Being anxious about that you are unable to deliver the correct message to others or you cannot use the correct words to influence on the other people or using the same words every time in every situation. If you have these thoughts while speaking, then you have a problem to express yourself in that target language.

A person without oral communication skills will suffer in this era of competition and may find it difficult to achieve a higher score. Working in a team is essential but many students find working in a group as complicated work because they can never express their own ideas, they can never contribute an idea to the group (Singh, M.S, 2007).

English teacher plays a key role in the development of students' oral speech. Teachers who teach speaking skill highly required having a lot of experience in teaching this course. It is not only a matter to explain the material to students effectively, but also to have strategies to encourage students to be talkative in teaching and learning speaking process. “As teachers, however, we must be mindful that speaking involves more than simply using words to articulate what we are thinking, and there is more at play than simply asking students to say the words that they know” (Senior teacher Sarvinoz Suyunovna Mustafayeva). They need to encourage the students. So what should be done to improve the speaking skills in general?

METHODS

It is vital that you feel confident while speaking. Just like improving your writing, listening, reading or other skills there are techniques/methods you can use to improve your spoken English. According to Brown (2004: 141-142), there are five basic types of speaking, they are imitative, intensive, responsive, interactive, and extensive

Microskills of oral communication by Brown

1. Produce chunks of language of different lengths.
2. Orally produce differences among the English phonemes and allophonic variants.
3. Produce English stress patterns, words in stressed and unstressed positions, rhythmic structure, and intonational contours.
4. Produce reduced forms of words and phrases.
5. Use an adequate number of lexical units (words) in order to accomplish pragmatic purposes.
6. Produce fluent speech at different rates of delivery.
7. Monitor your own oral production and use various strategic devices—pauses, fillers, self-corrections, backtracking—to enhance the clarity of the message.
8. Use grammatical word classes (nouns, verbs, etc.), systems (e.g., tense, agreement, pluralization), word order, patterns, rules, and elliptical forms.
9. Produce speech in natural constituents—in appropriate phrases, pause groups, breath groups, and sentences
10. Express a particular meaning in different grammatical forms.
11. Use cohesive devices in spoken discourse.
12. Accomplish appropriately communicative functions according to situations, participants, and goals.
13. Use appropriate registers, implicature, pragmatic conventions, and other sociolinguistic features in face-to-face conversations.
14. Convey links and connections between events and communicate such relations as main idea, supporting idea, new information, given information, generalization, and exemplification.
15. Use facial features, kinesics, body language, and other nonverbal cues along with verbal language to convey meanings.
16. Develop and use a battery of speaking strategies, such as emphasizing key words, rephrasing, providing a context for interpreting the meaning of words, appealing for help, and accurately assessing how well your interlocutor is understanding you.

1. Learning through imitation (Speech Shadowing)

Imitating is copying words or actions. When we say imitation we are not talking about repeating after native speakers using the exact words to improve your speaking/pronunciation. We are talking about a little more difficult than that. While watching movies or TV shows with subtitles you should copy the conversations. Copy the speech pattern as best as you can. That is the way for babies to learn the language.

2. Intensive Speaking

This includes any kind of speaking performance. For example, reading aloud a text, sentence/ dialogue completion task or give a direct answer for simple questions.

3. Responsive Speaking

This is an effective way for student to speak. It should be in a limited level of a short conversation. Like quick replies/responses to teacher or student-initiated questions. This also includes question and answer, giving instructions and directions, paraphrasing, standard greeting and small talk, simple comment, and request.

4. Interactive Speaking

It is a complex interaction which includes multiple exchanges or multiple participants. Extended form of responsive language, such as an interview, role play, conversations, discussions, games.

5. Extensive Speaking (monologue)

This skill can be used by intermediate to advanced levels. It includes oral reports, summaries, presentations, picture-cued storytelling, re-telling a story, news event.

Activities to promote speaking

Discussions. After a lesson, discussions can be held for several reasons. After explaining the topic, teacher should create groups among students then students need to give their thoughts or ideas about the topic. For example, students can take part agree/disagree discussions. It is essential that every group member has to take part in discussion. The speech about the given topic should be equally divided among group members. The aim of doing this should only be express support, check for clarification, delivering exact ideas and so on.

Role Play. One other way of improving speaking ability is role-playing. In this activity learners should be actors/actresses. In role-play activities, the teacher gives information to the learners such as what kind of situations they are in, who they are and others.

Simulations. This activity is similar to role play activity. But Simulations are more detailed. In this activity students need to fetch items to the class in order to create a real scenario. For example, if learner is acting like a hairdresser, she should bring scissors to cut clients hair.

Information Gap. In this activity learners work as pairs. Information is provided for each of them. One student will have the information that other partner does not have and the partners will share their information. If one of the learners do not take part in this game the order of the information will not be completed. That's why every participants play a significant role.

Brainstorming. Teacher gives a topic. In a limited time every student should give their own ideas about this topic. Either group brainstorming or single brainstorming is effective. No one is not criticized for their ideas. Everyone can express their own opinions freely. So, feel free to give your ideas in this game.

Storytelling. Students need to summarize the tale or story they heard from somebody beforehand. They also can tell riddles or jokes.

Interviews. In this activity students get an interview from someone. Students should prepare their own interview questions. They also can interview each other.

Story Completion. This is very entertaining activity. A teacher starts to tell a story, but after a few sentences, he/she stops narrating and the rest begin to proceed from the point where the previous one stopped. It can help to make up characters, events.

Here are also seven tips of improving your speaking

- While reading books listen to the audio version of it too.
- Record your voice.
- Learn whole sentences than a single word.
- Watch yourself speak to create confidence.
- Use mnemonics to memorise something
- Listen to English songs on your phone with any lyrics app

downloaded

If you follow the methods that are given to you, you can speak English fluently. The most crucial point you would get is before speaking in English you would be trying to start 'THINKING IN ENGLISH.' It sounds ridiculous but that is really the basic thing to be done. Imagine, you think in your mother tongue before speaking, you have to translate it into English every time before you speak it out. This consumes time and thus it affects your fluency (may be your confidence too due to the pause between the words/sentences). And it leaves not so good impression on the listener. If you do not want that to happen, you need to follow the instructions given step by step. Schools must also incorporate these methods into their own syllabus. As you imbibe all these into your routine, you will get better day by day. Once you get a hold, you will start to understand the grammar in a much better way and your vocabulary starts improving automatically. You will start making a speech in front of a few people and that makes you feel more confident. Soon after you found yourself speaking in front of 1000 odd people on a stage and it helps you let go of your stage fright.

To recapitulate, some methods and techniques can enhance students' speaking ability. English teachers also could affect their English speaking ability. In addition, high self-esteem, less anxiety and confidence are also essential in making expressing oneself fluently. Moreover, students must listen to English materials as well as speak in English, so that they can improve their English speaking ability. Speaking a foreign language can be a difficult but at the same time it is fun. You will unintentionally pick up the words and as soon as you get more familiar with those words, they will end up popping up in your everyday speech. This sort of practice will help you become fluent in the target language.

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